

Histology of the Thyroid and Parathyroid Glands of Cat

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Thyroid gland secretes tetraiodothyronine (T_4) and triiodothyronine (T_3) hormones. These hormones play an important role in energy metabolism, growth and differentiation of tissues. (Banks, 1981). Information on the histology of thyroid and parathyroid glands of cat is meagre. The present study was aimed to record the microscopic structure of the thyroid and parathyroid glands of cat.

Materials and Methods

Six adult cats including one pregnant cat were utilized for the present study. The thyroid and parathyroid glands were collected and preserved in 10% neutral buffered formalin (10% NBF). The tissue pieces were processed for paraffin sections of 5-6 micron thickness. The sections were subjected to Haematoxylin and Eosin method (Singh and Sulochana, 1997) for general histomorphology.

Results and Discussion

In the present study the thyroid gland was surrounded by a connective tissue capsule which was composed of collagen fibers, fibroblasts and blood vessels. The fine trabeculae extended from the capsule into the parenchyma of the gland and divided the gland into lobes and lobules.

Each lobule of thyroid gland consisted of aggregation of different sizes of follicles. The follicles were surrounded by a network of fine reticular fibers. Follicles were lined by simple

cuboidal to low columnar cells. Two types of follicles were observed viz., active and inactive follicles. Large numbers of parafollicular or C-cells were present in between the follicles. They were larger in size and their cytoplasm was lightly stained. They were arranged in groups between the follicles.

In pregnant cat no characteristic appearance of follicles was recorded. They were highly irregular in shape and follicles were smaller in size. Further, parafollicular cells were more in number than the non-pregnant cat. Most of the follicles were active type and they showed vacuoles in the colloid substance. The colloid substance was lightly stained in the thyroid gland of pregnant cat.

The parathyroid glands were enclosed by a common capsule with the thyroid glands. The parenchyma of organ consisted of different types of cells, connective tissue stroma and numerous blood capillaries. The cells were arranged as clusters, follicles and strands. The predominant cell type in the parathyroid was chief cells. The chief or principal cells were subdivided into light cells (inactive) and dark cells (active). The inactive cells were slightly larger and they were acidophilic in nature and showed a granular cytoplasm and their nucleus was vesicular. The dark cells were relatively smaller than the light cells. Their cytoplasm was highly acidophilic and contained numerous granules and their nuclei were darkly stained. In the present study, oxyphil cells were not observed in the parathyroid of cat.

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Fig 1. Photomicrograph of urinary bladder of cat showing propria submucosa (SM), Tunica muscularis (M) and Parasympathetic ganglion (G).

ganglions were enclosed by a connective tissue capsule. The intramural glanglionic neurons were parasympathetic in type. In the muscular coat of urinary bladder several nerve terminals were also observed close to the ganglions.

Summary

Urinary bladder of cat was divisible into vertex, body and a neck. The wall of the urinary bladder

consisted of distinct mucosa, *tunica muscularis* and *tunica serosa*. The muscular tunic of urinary bladder of cat consisted of three layers viz., inner, middle and outer layers. Intramural ganglion cells were noted in the muscular coat of urinary bladder in cat. The glanglionic neurons were parasympathetic type.

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Fig. 1. Photomicrograph of thyroid gland of pregnant cat showing thyroid follicles (F), Follicular cells (C) and Para follicular cells (P). Haematoxylin and Eosin x 400

Fig. 2. Photomicrograph of parathyroid gland of cat showing capsule (C), light cells (L) and dark cells (D). Haematoxylin and Eosin x 400.

Summary

The thyroid gland was surrounded by a connective tissue capsule. The trabeculae divided the parenchyma of gland into different lobules. the parafollicular or C-cells were present in between the follicles, arranged as clusters between the follicles. In pregnant cat follicles were irregular in shape and smaller in size. Parafollicular cells were more in number than in the non-pregnant cat. Parathyroid cells

were arranged as clusters, follicles and strands. The predominant cell type of the organ included chief cells or principal cells. The oxyphil cells were not identified in the parathyroid of cat.

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